
Advocacy Beyond the Academy: The Baltimore Afro-American Support of Black Intellectuals, Carter G. Woodson, Rayford W. Logan, and Nnamdi B. Azikiwe

Baiyina W. Muhammad, Ph.D.

Associate Professor

Women's & Gender Studies Program

Department of History

Room 208-C, Edmonds Classroom Building

North Carolina Central University

Durham, North Carolina, 27707, USA

Abstract

This article examines the pivotal role of the Baltimore Afro-American, a leading Black newspaper of the early 20th century, in supporting the intellectual work and advocacy of Carter G. Woodson, Rayford W. Logan, and Nnamdi Azikiwe. It argues that the newspaper not only amplified Black scholarly voices but also cultivated a Pan-African consciousness among African American readers through its coverage of global Black struggles. By highlighting the Afro-American's strategic use of journalism to popularize historical knowledge, the article situates the newspaper as both a cultural mediator and an agent of racial uplift. Drawing on Woodson's foundational work in African American historiography, Logan's transnational perspective on Black education, and Azikiwe's engagement with African liberation, the article shows how these figures' intellectual contributions were amplified through the newspaper's pages. The article concludes that the Baltimore Afro-American served as an institutional ally, extending the reach of Black intellectual thought beyond academic spaces. It thus urges contemporary scholars to reconsider the role of Black newspapers as sites of intellectual production and political mobilization. By revisiting these historical collaborations, the article challenges conventional boundaries between academic and activist work and demonstrates how advocacy beyond the academy has long been central to Black intellectual traditions.

Keywords: Black press, Carter G. Woodson, African American history, Pan-Africanism, intellectual activism, Baltimore Afro-American

"Advocacy Beyond the Academy: The Baltimore *Afro-American* Support of Black Intellectuals, Carter G. Woodson, Rayford W. Logan, and Nnamdi B. Azikwe"

Either convince the world that you have a record as glorious as that of any other race or remain content with a fixed status of inferiority. The greatest scholars of today are saying that there is no such thing as race in science and that there is nothing in anthropology or psychology to support such myths as the inferiority or superiority of races. These truths, however, will have very little bearing on the uplift of the Negroes, if they are left in the state of academic discussion. There must be an actual demonstration. The Negro must learn his past and publish it to a prejudiced world. A man's social standing is determined largely by the record of his family. A nation is known for what it has achieved. The very name of Greek or Roman excites admiration: the mere mention of the word Negro arouses contempt. And yet the Negro has contributed as much to the welfare of mankind as the Greek or the Roman. The Negro himself, however, does not know it because his friends have not been anxious for him to learn his interesting story¹

Carter G. Woodson's promotion of the History Association Spring Conference, held at Virginia Normal School, 1926.

The Baltimore *Afro-American*, one of the leading Black newspapers of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, aimed to reconnect African Americans with Africa and other parts of the African Diaspora. Its goal was for African Americans to recognize the similarities in their individual and shared experiences with other Africans. For the African American, focusing on similarities helped to raise consciousness and foster Black solidarity worldwide. A clear example of the *Afro-American's* Pan-African agenda was its coverage of African and Caribbean struggles against European domination, as well as Black South Africans' fight against the post-World War II apartheid system and the celebration of political independence across Africa. However, the primary aim of this work is to examine writings by leading Black intellectuals who wrote for the newspaper, namely Carter G. Woodson, Rayford W. Logan, and Nnamdi Azikiwe, in their reporting for the Baltimore *Afro-American*. In so doing, the *Afro-American* news helped to expand the reach of Black intellectuals beyond the academy. The analysis focuses on articles written by and about Woodson, Logan, and Azikiwe in the *Afro-American News*, beginning in 1916, following the establishment of the Association for the Study of Negro Life (ASNL), through the 1930s.

Background

By 1920, the *Afro-American* had grown substantially and became one of the most prominent Black-owned newspapers in the country, with a circulation of 14,000 copies. In a 1920 letter to his family, Murphy Sr. expressed his confidence in himself and in his people's ability to succeed in civilization, as well as in the ultimate justice that would secure them full citizenship in the nation. Murphy's reflective letter was written in 1920 on his eightieth birthday and was opened and read at his hundredth birthday celebration. The letter he left behind was priceless. In it, he shared his thoughts and hopes for the *Afro-American* newspaper. Murphy wrote that, "the value of a newspaper is not solely determined by its buildings, its equipment, or its employees. Rather, a newspaper's success should be determined by its belief in itself, God,

and in the present generation." He hoped that the *Afro-American*, mainly comprised of the Murphy family, would evaluate itself using several key questions. First, did they remain true to the common people and help preserve the liberty and dignity of the race? Second, did they promote better jobs and proper housing for the community? Third, did they remain out of politics "except to expose corruption and condemn injustice, race prejudice and the cowardice of compromise." He also hoped that the *Afro-American* would uplift and help sustain the community it served and eventually become a daily paper. He was grateful to the paper's loyal supporters who believed in its honest and progressive nature, and he wanted those qualities to persist.

Murphy understood the challenges that were experienced by the members of the Black press. Although many of the challenges came from external forces, Murphy also understood and reflected on the internal struggle of managing a successful Black newspaper. However, he believed in Black progress, racial solidarity, and uplift. Murphy wrote, That it was difficult to educate the people up to the standard of reading a Negro newspaper. Both ignorance and prejudice had to be challenged within and outside the Black community. The clergymen, lettered men in both the bar and medical associations as well as businessmen initially did not see the value in the Black press. Nevertheless, the Black press had taken the doubts, criticism, and continued in the struggle for the race.

Murphy concluded that the advancement of the race was not being done through any other channels than the Black press. He argued that the Black press made bold stands for the rights that Black people were denied. He also suggested that the Black press presented the claims of the race for better things.²

Carl Murphy's forty-nine-year tenure as editor and leader of the *Afro-American Company* began in 1918 and ended in 1967. During his time, Carl contributed to the paper in many ways. He diligently and passionately covered a wide range of issues at both the national and international levels. Carl used the editorial page to challenge injustices at local, national, and international levels, including lynching, race and gender discrimination, poor housing, and substandard schools, all while advocating for full citizenship for all Americans. He launched an editorial critique against the U.S. government for its military occupation of Haiti. Carl sent *Afro-American* reporters abroad to cover the experiences of Black soldiers during World War II. After the war, he wrote in support of the decolonization of Africa. Carl often communicated with prominent leaders and the organizations they represented. These included Thurgood Marshall, NAACP legal counsel and later U.S. Supreme Court Justice; Walter White, another NAACP leader; Urban League executives Eugene K. Jones and Lester Granger; Mary McLeod Bethune of the National Council of Negro Women; and scholars such as W.E.B. Du Bois, Carter G. Woodson, Rayford Logan, Nnamdi Azikwe and countless others.³

Carl Murphy's youngest daughter, Frances L. Murphy II, described her father's commitment to civil rights struggles and his leadership of the newspaper. She detailed conversations between Murphy and influential Black leaders such as the *Crisis* editor and scholar W. E. B. Du Bois, former *Kansas City Call* editor and NAACP Executive Secretary Roy Wilkins, educator and activist Mary McLeod Bethune, and African American Congressman Oscar DePriest. Breakfast meetings often took place away from the *Afro's* main office, usually at

the Murphy home, to avoid interruptions. NAACP campaigns, political conferences, and hopeful candidates regularly sought support from Carl Murphy through the Afro American newspaper.

Frances recounted numerous occasions when Carl Murphy and Du Bois would walk through their Baltimore neighborhood, Morgan Park, together to discuss and strategize how to handle civil rights cases and necessary fundraising. Morgan Park was built in 1917 and attracted African American faculty and staff of Morgan College, as well as other members of the Black community, who sought decent housing for their families. Carl Murphy's role in the NAACP was head of the Legal Redress Committee during the early tenure of Thurgood Marshall. Murphy's main role was to raise money to fund court cases and pay attorney fees. Murphy was noted for giving his own money when he was unable to raise enough funds to cover legal fees and court costs. Frances recounted a statement made by Thurgood Marshall regarding Murphy's commitment to Civil Rights and his support of the NAACP. Marshall said that if it were not for Carl Murphy, there would have been no money to file court cases, such as those for equal salaries for Baltimore teachers, the integration of the fire and police departments, as well as challenges against the University of Maryland's admission policies.⁴

Carl Murphy, reminiscent of his father, had a clear vision for the newspaper. He aimed to expand the circulation of the *Afro-American* beyond Baltimore's Black community. Under his leadership, the newspaper continued its growth by establishing bureaus in Washington, D.C., Philadelphia, New York, Newark, and Richmond. There were even some subscribers in Africa. The strong leadership of Carl J. Murphy earned the *Afro-American* the title of the most successful Black publication in the mid-Atlantic region. Frances noted that the only difference between the national edition of the *Afro-American* in Baltimore and the other city editions was that local news in various cities was covered along with national news. The front page featured local news, but the editorial page remained largely unchanged. She also stated that Carl Murphy was very interested in helping readers understand the connection between their local experiences and national issues such as civil rights cases being filed in courts, school integration, equal pay, and equal employment. He often explained during meetings how each of the major stories would affect the others. As a result, managing editors and city editors were asked to keep these issues in mind when deciding on the layout of the paper.⁵

Like his father, Carl Murphy believed in equal rights for both men and women. Murphy encouraged all five of his daughters to learn the business, particularly since they were to inherit the company in the future. They were also encouraged to pursue academic careers in journalism and work for the *Afro-American*. Two of Carl Murphy's daughters, Frances L. Murphy II and Elizabeth Murphy Moss, became chief officers of the *Afro-American* Company after his death. Frances became Chair of the Board and Chief Executive Officer in 1971 until 1974, and Elizabeth became Vice President and Treasurer of the Company. Elizabeth Murphy had served as the first Black female war correspondent for the *Afro-American* during World War II. Carl Murphy's vision for the business also included equal pay and equal rights for both male and female reporters. Frances Murphy stated, "We had a fight going on for survival. The people in the white press did not have that kind of fight; they were just out there doing a job. Ours was more than a job, people depended on us."⁶

Carte G. Woodson and the *Afro-American*

Beginning in 1916, the *Afro-American* newspaper highlighted Carter G. Woodson's founding of the Association for the Study of Negro Life (ASNL) and his early efforts to promote Negro History Week in 1926. Scholars will find that prominent Black newspapers, such as the Chicago Defender, the Pittsburgh Courier, and the New York Age, among others, published Woodson's writings and followed his career until he died in 1950. In fact, many of Woodson's essays that appeared in the Black press remain obscure. In the *Afro-American* news alone, Carter G. Woodson was a regular presence. A total of 64 writings and essays by and about Woodson can be found between 1916 and 1933, when he published his seminal work "The Mis-Education of the Negro." It is not surprising that the *Afro-American* supported Woodson, Logan, and Du Bois's work; they added to the sophistication and integrity of the *Afro-American* news.

An essential aspect of the Baltimore *Afro-American* and Carter G. Woodson relationship is its focus on Woodson's coverage of Afro-Diasporic history. Using three writings authored by Woodson and published in the *Afro-American*, I propose to examine Woodson's creation and promotion of Negro History Week from a broader global perspective. This approach reflects Woodson's effort to advocate for the entire Negro race beyond academic circles. In effect, he taught a much wider Black community and used the pages of the press as his classroom.

"Negro was First to Discover America: He Taught the Modern World the use of Iron" Article featured during Negro History Week celebration, February 7 to 14th, 1926.

Woodson's central idea was that African Americans played a significant role among the pioneers of American history. Woodson cited research by Harvard University Professor, Lee Weiner, to support his thesis that Africans were the first to visit the shores of America. Weiner found evidence of African influences on the continent that predate European exploration. Woodson emphasizes for his readers the importance of Blacks in the Pacific, Mexico, Guatemala, Chile, Peru, and Venezuela as places where Africans accompanied European explorers. The article covered Black contributions to science, the military, art, business, and highlighted important Black orators and freedom fighters from Gabriel Prosser of Virginia to 20th-century figures like Kelly Miller, James Weldon Johnson, and W.E.B. DuBois.

The essay was published during the inauguration of Negro History Week and reflects the *Afro-American* newspaper's desire to reconnect with Africa and other parts of the Diaspora, aiming for African Americans to recognize the similarities in their individual and collective experiences with other Africans. These similarities were meant to increase their awareness and foster a sense of Black solidarity worldwide. Similarly, Carter G. Woodson believed that the study of history could serve as a tool for social and cultural change and should be based on thorough research. Additionally, Woodson thought it was equally important to involve working-class people, especially young people, in studying and learning history for self-affirmation and empowerment.

Later in 1931, during its coverage of the Firestone Rubber Company's labor scandal in Liberia, the U.S. occupation of Haiti, and the early reign of Haile Selassie as Ethiopia's new leader, the *Afro* published an essay by Woodson that read: "Whites Plan to Exterminate Tribes and Make Africa White Man's Country." In the essay, Woodson argues that, "exploiting

Europeans have control of practically all the continent except Liberia and Abyssinia, and in the South, they have dreamt of ridding the region of its native inhabitants."

Plan to Exterminate the natives:

Woodson cited European efforts to exploit continental Africans as an ongoing struggle that should concern Black people everywhere. Woodson submitted his essay after attending a speech given by Thomas Jesse Jones, a white businessman whom Woodson regarded as "the white boss of African Negroes." Jones's speech was an appeal to his fellow white business owners. Throughout the essay, Woodson provides readers with excerpts of Jones's speech. Jones petitioned white business owners to travel to Africa for commercial enterprise. He also celebrated the future prospect of the complete extermination of the natives and his desire to make the continent a white man's country. Jones proclaimed,

The natives would be exterminated by the extension of the liquor traffic, by the spreading of the white man's venereal diseases among them, by dispossessing them of their best land, by forcing them to toil as slaves, and by the general program of segregation by which the blacks, getting so much less out of life than the whites, will not be able to survive.

Woodson draws his readers in by linking Jones' address to white business owners with European colonial rule in Africa. Woodson maps the various systems of colonization Africans experienced by explaining the relationship between exploitation in southern Africa and European exploitation of West Africa. He argued that the West African situation at the time was not as discouraging as it had become further south among the South African Union.

Woodson also acknowledged the shift in attitude among European missionaries from focusing on enterprise to paying more attention to education for the masses. He noted that the missionaries were the first to pave the way for foreign intervention. Woodson emphasized that businessmen like Thomas Jesse Jones, along with the help of missionaries, realized that the complete destruction of native populations was ultimately unnecessary because their labor was needed to develop the rich continent. Therefore, providing proper education for Africans would be essential for the security and benefit of European interests and wealth. Woodson equated Negro education in Africa with Negro education in America, which he reasoned, "must be carefully worked out and directed by the exploiters of the race."

Woodson informed *Afro* readers about the precarious situation all racial uplift workers in Africa faced because they had to conform to this policy. He pointed to Max Yergen as an example of an uplift worker, due to Yergen's status as the most well-known colored missionary in Africa. Yergen was prevented from taking his post in Liberia for several years because Thomas Jesse Jones opposed his appointment. Woodson viewed Yergen and other uplift workers as people who did not agree with the capitalistic approach to education being implemented in Africa as well as in America. He stated:

It seems to indicate that in the continent there will be an unnecessary division of opinion with respect to the practical and classical education which once divided the Negro in the United States. Whether in America or in Africa, the Negro needs an educational program developed from his own situation and based upon his own life. The Negro should be trained to do and also to think. All elements of his African environment should be considered in working out his program. The missionaries from afar may bring the natives the fundamentals, but in the final

analysis the Africans must educate themselves. More reader will find it difficult to have patience with the theory that the true remedy is that the poor shall be more industrious, when, as all know, they are already more industrious than the rich.

Woodson offers this observation as an intervention to address the ills found not only in the American educational system, but also in Colonial Africa. What makes this essay even more striking is that it was written two years before the publication of the *Mis-Education of the Negro*. Woodson held the firm belief that the type of education that was made available to African and African descendants strongly oriented Blacks toward a deplorable and diminished place in history and society. Woodson viewed the study of history as being interconnected with other academic disciplines and societal norms. Thus, his prescription called for the engagement of a broad public to study the Black past, which he believed would help Black people gain self-knowledge and self-respect as well as to regenerate positive race relations in all areas.

Finally, in one of the last essays published in 1933, the same year as the release of *The Mis-Education of the Negro*, *The Afro* highlighted a recent address that Woodson delivered to the local Philomathean Club of Baltimore.

In his lecture, Carter G. Woodson addressed four major themes that illuminated the complexity of the African American experience. He began by examining the triangular slave trade, outlining the transatlantic route that connected Africa, the West Indies, and the United States. He emphasized that enslaved Africans were often Europeanized in the West Indies before arriving in the American colonies, highlighting a process of cultural transformation prior to their forced labor in the U.S. Woodson then identified several areas deserving deeper scholarly inquiry, such as the psychological and cultural effects of the slaves' stopover in the Caribbean, and the rich insights to be gained from studying advertisements for runaway or for-sale slaves—many of whom were portrayed as intelligent and multilingual. Turning to broader ideological influences, Woodson argued that revolutionary ideals, particularly those stemming from the American and French Revolutions, had a profound effect on enslaved communities. He observed that, before 1825, slavery appeared to be in decline and that widespread emancipation outside of South Carolina and Georgia seemed imminent. Finally, Woodson challenged prevailing notions of rigid racial boundaries in early colonial America by suggesting that the “color line” had once been more fluid. He pointed to instances of intermarriage between slaves and indentured servants as evidence that racial divisions had not always been so starkly drawn.

Carter G. Woodson was indeed a scholar and worked tirelessly to promote the study and celebration of the global Black experience. He left several prestigious appointments within the academy, including Dean of the School of Library Arts at Howard University and Dean of West Virginia Collegiate Institute, to utilize the pages of the Black press and the Association for the Study of Negro Life and its publications to reach a broader public. Many of the ideals that Woodson upheld were also shared by the *Afro-American* newspaper and its president and chief editor, Carl Murphy.

Murphy's role as the president and chief editor of the *Afro-American* significantly influenced the news coverage related to the Diaspora. Like Woodson, Murphy was highly educated and well-traveled. He had established connections with many of the brightest and most knowledgeable scholars and students of the Diaspora. He often relied on their expertise to report

on the Diaspora, as shown in the cited essays. Using the African American intelligentsia to provide their analyses on the plight of Africans abroad was a key part of the *Afro-American's* mission to build Diaspora connections. Contributing writers and scholars such as Rayford Logan, W.E.B. Dubois, Carter G. Woodson, and others enhanced the sophistication and integrity of the Afro American news. The *Afro-American* selected contributing scholars who were leading advocates of Pan-African ideals, which it strongly supported.

Finally, in a 1930's article the *Afro* proudly declared Woodson and by extension the Association for the Study of Negro Life and History as a visionary for the ages.

Thousands of men and women have been able to take a neglected and despised cause like the chronicling of history of a lowly people, and collection of ancient documents bearing upon such a chronicle, and through the magic of sincerity, persistence and clear vision lift it to a place of dignity and respect...Our white folk lament that Negroes have never built a civilization, and men like Dr. Woodson rise up and point to the thick lips and kinky hair of the sphinx... Dr. Woodson has worked without ceasing, His important book, "The Negro in our History" which has gone through four editions, is probably more widely known among school children than any other single book...Some other important Woodson books in the past fifteen years include, The Education of the Negro prior to 1861, History of the Negro Church, African Myths, Negro Makers of History, Free Negro Heads of Families in the United States in 1830, and Negro Orators and Orations.

Teachers have been enlightened and inspired by Dr. Woodson, who in his lectures all across the country and by means of the annual meeting of the association, has educated the teachers as well as the public concerning the wide field of Negro History and the satisfying results which may be achieved by a thorough study.

The fact that the history association has not been able to pay Dr. Woodson a salary may be regarded as evidence of the public's failure to appreciate the services of the historian and the history association. On the other hand, there are signs of increasing public regard for Dr. Woodson, and his contribution to history, as well might there be. He has blazed a new trail. He has put old truths to new light. He has brought a new light to those who sat in darkness. He has made it possible for every Negro lad to hold his head a little higher and set his chin a little firmer. He has made it possible for a race to face the future with greater hope because he has taken the cover off the past.

Two or three more men like Dr. Woodson and even inaccurate news like "Time" will cease claiming the Egyptians and the Abyssinians for the white race.

"The Association for the Study of Negro Life and History has been able to Balance its Annual Budget of 20,000 because the Director, Dr. Carter G Woodson has served without compensation," Baltimore Afro American, November 9, 1930.

Rayford W. Logan and the *Afro-American*

Alongside its sharp-witted journalists, The Afro-American Newspaper also relied on prominent intellectuals for news reports and their insightful political commentary. Rayford W. Logan, one of the most distinguished historians of the African Diaspora experience, was asked

by the Afro-American News to provide an exclusive report on his trip to Haiti and to offer political commentary on the experiences of Haitians under U.S. occupation.⁷

Logan was an intellectual, a civil rights activist, and a Pan-Africanist. He maintained relationships with many of the prominent African American leaders of the twentieth century, including Du Bois, a labor union organizer. Philip Randolph, NAACP chairman, Walter White, historian and scholar, Carter G. Woodson, educator and activist, Mary McLeod Bethune, and many others. Logan earned a doctorate in history from Harvard University in 1936. During World War I, he had spent several years serving in the U.S. Armed Forces. Upon his honorary discharge, he journeyed throughout Europe as a way to escape the harsh racial climate that existed in the U.S. during the early twentieth century. While residing in Europe, Logan began to acquaint himself with the African American expatriate community in France. Logan joined the Pan-African Association and assisted Du Bois and Blaise Diagne in organizing the 1921 Pan-African Congress. Du Bois appointed Logan as the Assistant Secretary of the Bureau and interpreter for the Pan-African Association.⁸

Logan and other members of the Pan-African Association supported Du Bois's Pan-African agenda. During the first half of the twentieth century, Pan-African ideals did not promote African independence. Instead, Pan-Africanism embraced Western principles of equality and democracy. While its advocates protested racial discrimination and European colonization, they adopted Western democratic ideals as the foundation of their political and intellectual efforts. However, by the second Pan-African Congress in 1921, Du Bois had taken a more assertive stance, speaking firmly against racial discrimination and in favor of self-governance for Africa. The manifesto adopted by the Congress was highly critical of colonial powers, including Belgium, Spain, Portugal, and France. It called on the League of Nations to recognize Liberia, Ethiopia, Haiti, and the Dominican Republic as independent nations. The Congress also demanded eventual self-governance for colonized African nations and condemned racial discrimination.

Logan's interest in U.S. policy in Haiti grew out of his work with the Pan-African Congress of 1921 and 1923. He had several encounters with some of the world's premier political leaders. More importantly, he developed a friendship with Dantes M. Bellegarde, Haitian Minister to France and Haitian Delegate to the Assembly of the League of Nations. Bellegarde became Logan's mentor on Caribbean affairs. Bellegarde not only invited Logan to Haiti but also financed his trip. Logan traveled to Haiti in 1926 to investigate the U.S. occupation. Upon his return from Haiti Logan published several articles about the occupation, which appeared in *Opportunity* and in *The Nation*.⁹

By 1927, Logan enrolled in a Master of Arts program at William College. Without needing to spend time in residence, Logan was able to complete the M.A. degree in two years. His major course of study was American history with a minor in government. Logan's focus was on U.S. policy in the Caribbean. By June 1929, Logan submitted his thesis on the history of education in Haiti, which was later published in the *Journal of Negro History*. Logan's work with the Pan-African Association and many of its supporters, along with his travels to Haiti, helped shape his ideology and scholarship. It seems clear that Logan was chosen by the Afro-American News to investigate and report on the end of U.S. occupation in Haiti because of their shared ideological views, which formed the foundation of the Pan-African Agenda.

Rayford W. Logan covered the Cuban Revolution for the *Afro-American* and agreed to cover the U.S. Marine corps' withdrawal from Haiti. He wrote reports on the condition of Haiti solely for the *Afro American*. Weeks prior to Logan's travel, the *Afro-American* printed an editorial entitled, "The World is as Close as Your Afro." The editorial provided a brief discussion of why *Afro* writers travel to significant areas of the Diaspora to report the news. The *Afro* clearly outlined to its readers that Diaspora news coverage was important for showing solidarity among the "dark races," awakening readers' consciousness, and demonstrating kinship between all people in the struggle for social and economic justice.¹⁰

Although Logan agreed to write for the *Afro-American* about Haiti, his primary reason for traveling to Haiti was to search for newspaper files and other materials for his doctoral dissertation on American interest in Haiti. Logan was detained for one week before boarding a U.S. ship to travel to Haiti because of its Jim Crow policy of segregation. After arriving in Haiti on July 14, 1934, Logan cabled three reports to the *Afro-American*. The reports reflected Logan's interpretation of the spirit of Haitians, the impact of American occupation on poor Haitians, and discussed the Haitian transportation system, health, education, and the Haitian military.¹¹

The gains made in Haiti regarding health and sanitation were seen as a positive result of U.S. control. However, aside from the agricultural and industrial schools, there were no adequate normal schools for men and women in Haiti. More importantly, Haiti lacked a university after two decades of U.S. oversight. Logan urged Black Americans and other Haitian allies to advocate for the establishment of a university in Haiti, funded by American investors who had profited from their control over Haiti's finances. Logan suggested that Haiti's future looked more promising than Cuba's, which remained embroiled in conflict even after its political and social revolution had concluded. He noted, however, that their experience under U.S. rule had not broken the Haitian spirit. He credited their resilience to over a century of independence— independence won against Napoleon's best troops—and Haiti's ability to remain independent despite hostility from every "civilized" country. Although Logan expressed concerns about U.S. capitalist interests and investments in Haiti, he was reassured that capitalism had not penetrated Haiti as deeply as it had in Cuba. Logan saw Haitian peasants as being as independent as they had been before the occupation. Small landholdings traditionally worked by Haitian peasants remained intact, though few Haitians owned land outright.

In his discussion of the markets in Port-au-Prince and the transportation system, Logan focused on the deficiencies present in both. The roads in Haiti, which Americans had previously claimed were excellent, were described as unsafe. Unlike American roads made of concrete, Haiti's roads were dirt and stone and frequently closed after heavy rains. The most reliable and affordable mode of transportation on these unreliable roads was donkeys. Logan saw Haitians traveling to the markets in Port-au-Prince to buy and sell produce, only to return home with little money and a few items purchased in the city. Haitian peasants were often undernourished and did not benefit from the economy as much as American capitalists did.

Logan witnessed the ceremony that marked the end of the American occupation. In his report to the *Afro-American*, Logan questioned what role the Haitian army would have in Haiti's future. He offered hope that its role would be different from that of the former military, which wielded political power. Consequently, the new Haitian army would primarily be occupied with policing the country, making it improbable that it could become involved in political plots.

Logan concluded by noting that the new military would be subordinate to the civil authority, which could not be overthrown by a military coup, as had been the case in the past.¹²

In its August 11, 1934, edition, the editorial section of the *Afro-American* had a brief commentary on the newspaper's response to the end of the U.S. occupation. The editorial first praised Rayford Logan for reporting on Haiti. Second, it offered criticism to the defenders of U.S. aggression who declared that the occupation made Haiti better off. Finally, the *Afro-American* doubted whether the U.S. was truly out of Haiti, as fiscal controls, as noted by Rayford Logan, remained through the Bank of Haiti. The *Afro-American* warned its readers to be skeptical of President Roosevelt's New Deal, which may have formally taken the U.S. out of Haiti, but not U.S. bankers.¹³

The *Afro-American* continued to show interest in Haiti after the U.S. withdrew in 1934. The paper reported on the New York Commission's trip to Haiti that year. The Commission represented the Haitian Afro-American Chambers of Commerce. The visit by the Commissioner, which was suggested by Haiti's new President Stenio Vincent, was strongly supported by the *Afro-American*. The paper was interested in the commission for two main reasons. First, because it represented both African Americans and Haitians. Second, because the two groups were working together to build an economic coalition, which appealed to the *Afro-American*. After the Commission returned from Haiti, the *Afro-American* published several articles and editorials about the new financial relationship developing between Black Americans and Haitians.¹⁴

Nnamdi B. Azikwe and the *Afro-American*

Another writer whom the *Afro-American* hired to cover issues relating to the African Diaspora was Nnamdi Ben Azikiwe. Azikiwe was born in Zungeru, Nigeria, and came to the U.S. to pursue higher education. He would eventually become a key leader in the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC) in 1944, and the first president of an independent Nigeria in 1960. Azikiwe worked as a featured writer for the Baltimore *Afro-American* while studying at Lincoln University during the 1930s. Azikiwe's contribution to the *Afro-American* news began during the Liberian Labor scandal from 1929 to 1934. The scandal not only led Azikiwe to write several editorials for the newspaper but also to study, publish, and publicly speak about the labor scandal, thereby entering the debate among leaders of the African American community regarding the plight of Liberia. Azikiwe also challenged the notion put forth primarily by the U.S., which regarded Liberia as a failed colony that was unable to be governed by Blacks.¹⁵

During his tenure at Lincoln, Azikiwe was drawn to Liberia as a subject of interest. The Liberian labor crisis was a significant point of discussion on the political front, internationally and nationally, within and outside the Black community. Liberia was brought to the attention of Nnamdi through correspondence with friends George Padmore, a native of Trinidad, and Phillip Davies of Liberia. Both Padmore (Malcolm I. Nurse the name he used at this time) and Davies were students at Fisk University. The African students formed a political organization for foreign Black students studying in American colleges and universities. The primary objective of the newly formed organization was to foster racial consciousness and a spirit of nationalism, aiming at the protection of Liberian sovereignty. The organization based its framework on the Kuomintang Party, which was founded by Chinese students studying at Western universities.¹⁶ The organizations worked to stimulate interest among African students to focus their intellectual

efforts toward Africa. Second, they aimed to hasten the African Renaissance and actively contribute to preparing Africans for the future of African nationalism.¹⁷

It was during his involvement with the African student organization that Azikiwe's obsession with Liberia and other African affairs began. He started studying Liberian history and government, and by 1931, he was ready to present a paper before the Association for the Study of Negro Life and History. Also, during this period, Azikiwe sent several letters to the *Afro-American* editor of the newspaper concerning the organization's stance on the labor crisis and the findings of the U.S. Slavery Investigation Commission. Azikiwe accused the *Afro-American* and other Western organizations of condemning Liberia without fully understanding its history, culture, and relationship with major world powers.

Later, the *Afro* printed an article submitted by Azikiwe after he traveled to Liberia to research the country. Azikiwe's contribution to Liberia went beyond the *Afro-American* news; he also published 'Liberia in World Politics' in the *Journal of Negro History* in 1934. However, by 1933, Azikiwe's opposition toward the *Afro-American* news had been resolved. After the *Afro-American* sent its editor, William N. Jones, on a goodwill mission to Liberia to uncover the truth about the labor situation, Azikiwe became very supportive of the newspaper and its new stance on Liberian affairs. Although he did not contribute to the newspaper's editorials following the labor scandal, his involvement was valuable. Certainly, it helped maintain the integrity of the *Afro-American*, influencing Nnamdi's journalistic interest and style. He later mentioned that his work as a resident correspondent for the *Afro* helped him launch his newspaper, *The West African Pilot*. His radical, Pan-African newspaper eventually became the leading African publication in the fight against European imperialism.¹⁸

Conclusion

Sending its reporters worldwide in search of news or commissioning reports from noted scholars or leaders in the Black community who were knowledgeable about the Diaspora made it possible for the *Afro-American* to provide its readers with firsthand information. The editors of the *Afro-American* also believed that sending their reporters throughout parts of the Diaspora to report firsthand news would create unity in thought among African descendants worldwide. They aimed to establish a Pan-African solidarity that would bolster the Black struggle for social, political, and economic justice. Several supporting factors suggest that the *Afro-American* adopted a high level of commitment to African Diaspora communities. During the occupation of Haiti, *Afro-American* president and chief editor Carl Murphy traveled to Haiti along with the Moton Commission members and reported Haitian news to the paper. In 1933, William N. Jones, *Afro* editor, received an invitation from Liberian Minister Barclay to travel to Liberia as its goodwill ambassador. Jones not only reported his findings to the *Afro* but also developed an economic plan for Liberia entitled the "Save Liberia Plan." The plan was designed to build networks between Liberians and African Americans. The use of the Black intelligentsia to report, analyze, and spread news about the struggles of Africans abroad was another strategy adopted by the *Afro-American*.

Contributing writers and scholars, such as Carter G. Woodson, Rayford Logan, and Nnamdi Azikiwe, among others, elevated the level of sophistication and credibility of the *Afro-American* news. Not only were key leaders selected, but those who strongly supported Pan-

African ideology, which the paper fully endorsed. The publisher, editors, and writers of the *Afro-American* supported and planned for political networks and economic connections with Blacks in Haiti and Liberia. Regarding the crisis in Ethiopia, the *Afro-American* encouraged African American involvement in the conflict, Black migration to Ethiopia, and political links between Diaspora communities. The *Afro-American's* relationship with Black intellectuals and their responses to questions of identity were reflected in their weekly coverage of Diaspora news.

Endnotes

¹*AfroAmerican*, “History Association Ready for MEET”

²Baltimore *Afro American* Magazine Section, “History Series: John Murphy Sr., August 24, 1974.

³Francis Louise Murphy II, “Women In Journalism,” interview by Fern Ingersoll, videotaped, October 25, 1991 through December 3, 1992, Washington Press Club Foundation, Washington, D.C. Frances L. Murphy is one of Carl Murphy’s five daughters. In 1972, Frances L. Murphy became president of the *Afro American* after her cousin the late John H. Murphy III. The paper’s current publisher is John Oliver Jr., Carl Murphy’s great nephew. In this interview Frances Murphy provides very pertinent and useful information about Carl Murphy and other members of the Murphy family who played a vital role in the Afro American company. She notes that many of his editorials were written using a different name, namely John Jasper. He often wrote without ascribing his signature to the editorial to see if he could get a reaction from the readers. She noted that Carl Murphy wrote most of the editorials for the paper, and when he didn’t write them, he provided the outline for the editorials.

⁴*Ibid.* Frances stated that her father usually relied on friends and networks within the Black community for economic support. He solicited funds both by telephone and through letters. However, she did state that, people outside the Black community made financial contributions to the NAACP’s defense fund as well.

⁵“The Afro: Seaboard’s Largest Weekly,” *The Crisis*, (1938). Baltimore *Afro American*, March 17, 1971. See also, Carl Murphy, “Text of Address by Dr. Carl Murphy accepting the 40th Spingarn Medal,” (speech presented at the 40th Spingarn Medal NAACP’s Annual Convention in Atlantic City, New Jersey on June 24, 1955) in Beulah M. Davis Room, Special Collections, Morgan State University, Baltimore, Maryland. Also see, Frances L. Murphy II, interview. She gave an example of her father’s weekly comments about making the connection between national and local news. During meetings with the editors from each *Afro* branch Murphy said, “Okay, this story is going to impact this one. Don’t forget to look at that Richmond story and try to pick up a paragraph or two from that.”

⁶*Ibid.*, Carl Murphy’s daughters received their undergraduate degrees from the University of Minnesota, University of Wisconsin, and at Howard University. Frances Murphy said that her father assigned stories equally to both male and female reporters. She highlights the fact that, like her male counterparts, she had to cover tough stories and was even assigned as a police reporter for some time. As a police reporter she was often the only female reporter among mostly white males. She also added, “Black women have a different perspective on life than other people- my whole thought has been that we’ve been out there for so long that when people talk about different challenges, it’s the same challenges we’ve had all our lives. When people are talking about standing shoulder to shoulder to men, we’ve always done that. So we have a different way of accepting challenges because we’ve been challenged for so long.”

⁸Kenneth Robert Janken, *Rayford Logan and the Dilemma of the African American Intellectual*, (Boston: University of Massachusetts Press, 1993), 48.

⁹*Ibid.*

¹⁰Rayford W. Logan, “The Hazed in Haiti,” *The Nation*, (March 16, 1927), vol 124 no 3219: 281-283., See also, Logan, “The New Haiti,” *Opportunity*, (April, 1927), 101-103. In both articles Logan provides a critical analysis of the U.S. occupation of Haiti based on his personal experience as a traveler in Haiti. In the first article he highlights the grave injustice that Haitians encountered on several levels. The Haitian Departments of Commerce, Interior, Justice and Religion, and Education were threatened by American administrators to either submit willingly to American control or face starvation, which had already plagued the masses in Haiti. In sum Logan was convinced that under U.S. control Haitians fell into two categories: 1) those working for the occupation, or 2) those working for the Haitian government, which according to Logan had been absorbed by American experts. In the latter article Logan retaliated against Dr. Elmwood Mead, an American Administrator in Haiti. Logan responded to an article Mead had written earlier. Both Logan and Mead were in Haiti at the same time but came away with differing opinions regarding the situation in Haiti. Logan charged Mead with falsifying information about the success of the occupation. Logan also criticized American government officials, particularly Franklin D. Roosevelt and Smedley Butler, for discarding the right of Haitians to vote, elect their legislature, and receive proper training for self-governance.

¹¹Baltimore *Afro American*, February 3, 1934.

¹²*Ibid.*, July 28, August 11, 18, 25, 1934.

¹³*Ibid.*, August 11, 1934.

¹⁴*Ibid.*

¹⁵*Ibid.*, August 25, September 1, 8, 29, 1934.

¹⁶Baltimore *Afro American*, November 28, 1931, December 10, 1932. See also, Ben N. Azikiwe, "In Defense of Liberia," *Journal of Negro History*, XVII, 1(January, 1932): 30-50

¹⁷*Ibid.*, 85.

¹⁸*Ibid.*, 96-97. See also, Azikiwe, *My Odyssey* (1970), 138.

¹⁹Baltimore *Afro American*, "The Afro Policy Toward Liberia Changed," November 18, 1933, March 17, 1934. Also see, *My Odyssey: An Autobiography*, (New York: Praeger 1970), 305-306.

References

- Azikiwe, Nnamdi. 1934. *Liberia in World Politics*. London: A.H. Stockwell,
- Logan, Rayford W. "The Education of the Negro in Haiti." *Journal of Negro History*. vol 15 (1930): 401-60.
- Woodson, Carter G. 1933. *The Mis-Education of the Negro*. Associated Publishers.
- Woodson, Carter G. 1922. *The Negro in Our History*. Associated Publishers.
- Woodson, Carter G. 1915. *The Education of the Negro Prior to 1861*. Associated Publishers.
- Woodson, Carter G. 1921. *History of the Negro Church*. Associated Publishers.
- Woodson, Carter G. 1928. *Negro Makers of History*. Associated Publishers.
- Woodson, Carter G. 1924. *Free Negro Heads of Families in the United States in 1830*. Associated Publishers.
- Woodson, Carter G. 1925. *Negro Orators and Their Orations*. Associated Publishers.